

Electromagnetic quantum vacuum, the universal source of light, matter and antimatter.

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Abstract

Without stating any assumptions or making postulates it is shown that the electromagnetic quantum vacuum, a real field, derives naturally from Maxwell's theory considering the vector potential quantization at a single photon state. It corresponds to the electromagnetic field ground state at zero frequency, a zero-energy cosmic field permeating all of space and having positive and negative components. The electromagnetic quantum vacuum is composed of *kenons* states ($\kappa\epsilon\nu 0 = \text{vacuum}$). Photons are local oscillations of *kenons* guided by a non-local vector potential wave function with quantized amplitude. It appears that the energy density corresponding to the electromagnetic quantum vacuum fluctuations could be more important in the THz region entailing a physical explanation of the cosmological constant considered responsible of the cosmic acceleration.

The electron and positron elementary charges derive naturally from the negative and positive components of the electromagnetic quantum vacuum field respectively and are directly related to the photon vector potential. The vacuum polarization is a direct consequence.

In addition, it is shown that the masses of all particles, leptons, mesons, baryons and antiparticles are states of the electromagnetic quantum vacuum and derive respectively from the negative and positive vacuum field. Furthermore, the particles-antiparticles masses can be expressed through the elementary charges and their magnetic moments entailing that the mass concept derives from charges. The equivalence between Newton's gravitational law and Coulomb's electrostatic law results straightforward.

Furthermore, we show that the gravitational constant G is expressed explicitly through the electromagnetic quantum vacuum constants putting in evidence the electromagnetic nature of gravity. We draw that G is the same for matter and antimatter. However, attraction or repelling between matter and antimatter depends on the sign of the particles and antiparticles magnetic moments. Gravitational repelling between matter and antimatter may occur in the case the product of the particle –antiparticle magnetic moments is positive.

The electromagnetic quantum vacuum appears to be the natural link between quantum electrodynamics, particle physics, gravitation and cosmology and constitutes a basic step towards a unified field theory. Photons as well as particles and antiparticles might emerge spontaneously in the universe from the quantum vacuum fluctuations as residues that remain stable in space.

Key words: photons, electromagnetic waves, electromagnetic quantum vacuum, antigravity, dark light, kenons, gravitation, matter-antimatter, electromagnetic push gravity, dark energy, cosmological constant, dark matter, elementary charges, mass-charge relation, cosmology, unified field theory.

Introduction

The Λ CDM (Lambda – Cold Dark Matter) cosmological model is considered today as the most plausible theory that has the merit to provide satisfactory answers to a large number of astrophysical observations. It is based on the enhanced Big Bang concept according to which the universe is homogeneous and whose main components are Dark Matter and Dark Energy. The last one is associated to the cosmological constant Λ , which is considered responsible for the observed cosmic acceleration [1-4].

However, besides the difficulty to conceive that the whole universe emerged from a singular point, some upsetting issues still remain such as, why did the Big Bang occurred and what happened before? Furthermore, in order to explain the horizon problem as well as the fact that the geometry of the universe is Euclidean (flat), a cosmic inflation model has been introduced [5]. But, what are the physical reasons that inflation occurred in the very first 10^{-30} seconds of the Big Bang expanding the universe at a tremendous rate, many orders of magnitude faster than the speed of light in vacuum?

What happened to antimatter?

Finally, quantum field theory fails by a factor of 10^{120} to give a precise estimation to the cosmological constant [6, 7], the worst discrepancy between theory and observation in the history of science.

The above drawbacks call the human intelligence to be humble in front of the immensity and complexity of the still unknown universe. All the cosmological theories, including the one presented here, are temporary attempts to explain the observations realized up to now using the present theoretical tools and they are finally condemned to be replaced in the future according to the new observations to come.

In what follows, we make an introduction to the fundamentals of Quantum Vacuum Gravitation and Cosmology. The electromagnetic quantum vacuum, namely Dark Light, corresponds to the electromagnetic field ground state and results naturally from Maxwell's theory by considering the vector potential quantization at a single photon level. It is a real field with positive and negative components permeating all of space and has electric potential dimension.

Photons are oscillations of the electromagnetic vacuum field while the lepton-antilepton elementary charges derive equally from this field and are related to photons.

The gravitational constant G is a vacuum property having electromagnetic nature and is the same for matter and antimatter. The masses of particles and antiparticles derive from the negative and positive components of the vacuum field respectively and have opposite sign entailing repulsive gravitational forces between matter and antimatter. We also draw that G is inversely proportional to the vacuum density of states and may not be a universal constant.

Fluctuations of the electromagnetic quantum vacuum generate transient states of photons that are plausible to compose the Dark Energy and transient pairs of charges (particles) that might contribute to the Dark Matter.

A small fraction of the vacuum transient photons as well as particles and antiparticles might definitely remain stable in space composing the observed energy and mass in the universe.

1. The electromagnetic quantum vacuum, the Dark Light

The electromagnetic field vector potential $\vec{\alpha}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t)$ with quantized amplitude for a cavity free k -mode photon with angular frequency ω_k and polarization λ (circular left or right) writes [8-14]

$$\vec{\alpha}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t) = \xi \omega_k \left[\hat{\epsilon}_{k\lambda} e^{i(\vec{k}\cdot\vec{r} - \omega_k t + \theta)} + cc \right] = \omega_k \vec{\Xi}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t) \quad (1)$$

where $\hat{\epsilon}_{k\lambda}$ is the complex polarization unit vector, \vec{k} the wave-vector with amplitude $|\vec{k}| = 2\pi / \lambda_k$, λ_k is the wavelength of the mode k , θ phase parameter and cc the complex conjugate (see Appendix 1). The vector potential amplitude quantization constant ξ has positive and negative value

$$\xi = \frac{\hbar}{4\pi e c} = \frac{1}{(4\pi)^2} \frac{e\mu_0}{\alpha} = \pm 1.747 \cdot 10^{-25} \text{ V m}^{-1} \text{ s}^2 \quad (2)$$

where e is the electron or positron charge, \hbar is Planck's reduced constant ($\hbar = h / 2\pi$), c the speed of light in vacuum, $\alpha \approx 1/137$ is the fine structure constant and μ_0 the vacuum magnetic permeability.

It is straightforward to show that the vector potential function $\vec{\alpha}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t)$ is a natural wave function for a free k -mode photon that can be suitably normalized (see Appendix 1).

It satisfies the *vector potential – energy* (wave – particle) equation for the photon

$$i \left(\frac{\xi}{\hbar} \right) \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \vec{\alpha}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t) = \left(\frac{\vec{\alpha}_{0k}}{\tilde{H}_k} \right) \vec{\alpha}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t) \quad (3)$$

where

$$\left(\frac{\vec{\alpha}_{0k}}{\tilde{H}_k} \right) = -i \left(\frac{\xi}{\hbar} \right) c \vec{\nabla}_k \quad (4)$$

and the operator $\vec{\nabla}_k$ acts upon the mode k .

The equation (3) expresses both the first (energy) and second (vector potential) quantization of the electromagnetic field.

It is clear that the constants \hbar and ξ characterize respectively the energy and the vector potential field quantization for a single photon state. The perfect symmetry between the expression of the photon energy $E_k = \hbar\omega_k$ and that of the vector potential amplitude $\alpha_{0k} = \xi\omega_k$ expresses the simultaneous wave-particle nature of the single photon through the *vector potential – energy* equation (3).

It is worth noticing that the amplitude of the electric field of a cavity free k -mode photon is proportional to the square of the angular frequency [10, 12]

$$|\vec{\mathcal{E}}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t)| = |-\partial\vec{\alpha}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t) / \partial t| \propto |\xi|\omega_k^2 \quad (5)$$

Obviously, for $\omega_k = 2\pi c / \lambda_k \rightarrow 0$ (that is for $\lambda_k \rightarrow \infty$) the photon energy, vector potential and electric field tend to zero. However, for $\omega_k = 0$ the resulting electromagnetic field ground state does not correspond to a perfectly empty space because the fundamental function $\vec{\Xi}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t)$ composing the vector potential expression (1) still subsists and writes in classical electromagnetic theory and QED [14-17]

$$\vec{\Xi}_{0\lambda} = \xi \left[\hat{\mathcal{E}}_{\lambda} e^{i\theta} + \hat{\mathcal{E}}_{\lambda}^* e^{-i\theta} \right] \quad (6a)$$

$$\vec{\Xi}_{0\lambda} = \xi \left[\hat{\mathcal{E}}_{\lambda} a_{k\lambda} e^{i\theta} + \hat{\mathcal{E}}_{\lambda}^* a_{k\lambda}^+ e^{-i\theta} \right] \quad (6b)$$

where in the QED expression (6b) we have used the creation $a_{k\lambda}^+$ and annihilation $a_{k\lambda}$ non-Hermitian operators respectively for a single k -mode and λ -polarization photon.

Hence, in total absence of energy, of vector potential as well as of electric and magnetic fields, $\vec{\Xi}_{0\lambda}$ is the electromagnetic field ground state, the electromagnetic quantum vacuum corresponding to light at zero frequency, “Dark Light”.

It is a real cosmic field permeating all of space ($\lambda_k \rightarrow \infty$) and according to the physical dimensions of ξ has electric potential nature with positive and negative components.

Now, the phase parameter θ may take any value and consequently the electromagnetic quantum vacuum is composed of all possible states $\vec{\Xi}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t)$ corresponding to all modes and polarizations that can be called “*kenons*” (from $\kappa\varepsilon\nu o = \text{vacuum}$)

$$\vec{\Xi}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t) = \xi \left[\hat{\mathcal{E}}_{k\lambda} e^{i(\vec{k}\cdot\vec{r} - \omega t + \theta)} + cc \right] \quad (7a)$$

$$\vec{\Xi}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t) = \xi \left[\hat{\mathcal{E}}_{k\lambda} a_{k\lambda} e^{i(\vec{k}\cdot\vec{r} - \omega t + \theta)} + cc \right] \quad (7b)$$

From equation (4), an angular frequency operator $\tilde{\Omega}$ can be readily defined [17]

$$\tilde{\Omega}_k = -ic\vec{\nabla}_k \quad (8)$$

Using (3) and (8), we get the equation governing the *kenons* in vacuum

$$i \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \begin{bmatrix} \vec{\Xi}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t) \\ \vec{\Xi}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t) \end{bmatrix} = \tilde{\Omega}_k \begin{bmatrix} \vec{\Xi}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t) \\ \vec{\Xi}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \vec{\alpha}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t) \\ \vec{\alpha}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t) \end{bmatrix} \quad (9)$$

Obviously, according to the last equation, photons (electromagnetic waves) are generated by the action of the angular frequency operator $\tilde{\Omega}_k$ upon the *kenons* $\vec{\Xi}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t)$ creating a real vector potential $\vec{\alpha}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t)$ of a k -mode photon. Consequently, photons are local oscillations of *kenons* over a wavelength, with circular polarization ($\lambda = \text{Left or Right}$), guided by a non-local vector potential wave function with the real amplitude $\alpha_{0k} = \xi\omega_k$ [10, 13, 14].

Thus, the electromagnetic quantum vacuum, that is Dark Light, is composed of *kenons* and Light (Electromagnetic Waves) is composed of photons which are *kenons* transformed by the angular frequency operator.

The vacuum electric permittivity ε_0 and magnetic permeability μ_0 are intrinsic physical characteristics of the electromagnetic vacuum and are expressed through the fundamental physical constants α , ξ , \hbar and the elementary charge e

$$\mu_0 = (4\pi)^2 \alpha \frac{\xi}{e} \quad ; \quad \varepsilon_0 = \frac{\mu_0}{(4\pi\alpha)^2} \frac{e^4}{\hbar^2} = \frac{\xi e^3}{\alpha \hbar^2} \quad (10)$$

It is straightforward to verify that the product of the last expressions gives directly the velocity of light in vacuum c .

$$\varepsilon_0 \mu_0 = \left(\frac{4\pi e \xi}{\hbar} \right)^2 = \frac{1}{c^2} \quad (11)$$

Finally, it can be easily demonstrated [17] that any particle moving in the electromagnetic quantum vacuum with an acceleration $\vec{\gamma}$ will experience the Fulling-Davies-Unruh temperature (Appendix 2)

$$T_H = \frac{\hbar}{2\pi c k_B} |\vec{\gamma}| \quad (12)$$

where k_B is Boltzmann's constant.

2. The electromagnetic quantum vacuum fluctuations, from QED to Cosmology

2.1 Transient photons from the electromagnetic quantum vacuum.

Dark Energy and the cosmic acceleration.

Quantum field theory fails to evaluate the vacuum energy density by a factor of 120 orders of magnitude. In fact, the zero-point energy levels of all fields, corresponding to the fundamental eigenstate of the harmonic oscillator Hamiltonian, yield an infinite vacuum energy density which when upper limited to Planck's energy ($\sim 10^{19} GeV$) gives the "astronomic" value $\sim 10^{110} J m^{-3}$, while the observed one is roughly $\sim 10^{-10} J m^{-3}$ [1].

This unphysical theoretical result, the worst ever in the history of science, is mainly due to the mathematical ambiguity during the field quantization procedure according to the harmonic oscillator model consisting of replacing commuting classical canonical variables of momentum and position by non-commuting quantum mechanics Hermitian operators [10, 14, 18].

Electromagnetic waves are not composed of harmonic oscillators and no experiment has ever demonstrated that a single photon state is a harmonic oscillator. It has to be emphasized that, in contrast with material oscillators, the zero-point energy in quantum field theory, $\sum_{k,\lambda} \hbar \omega_k / 2$, resulting from the

harmonic oscillator Hamiltonian, does not correspond to a physical state and this is what indeed the astrophysical observations confirm.

As frequently pointed out [10, 18], we recall that the interpretations of the spontaneous emission and the Lamb shift in QED are not due to the zero-point energy term $\sum_{k,\lambda} \hbar \omega_k / 2$ but to the properties of the

photon creation $a_{k\lambda}^+$ and annihilation $a_{k\lambda}$ operators respectively. As about the well-known Casimir effect, it has been demonstrated by different methods [14 and references therein] that it can be directly explained by using the source fields or Lorentz's forces without invoking at all the zero-point energy. It has to be underlined again that the zero-point energy term $\sum_{k,\lambda} \hbar \omega_k / 2$, being a constant, commutes with

all quantum mechanics Hermitian operators corresponding to physical observables and consequently has absolutely no influence to any physical process.

Conversely, it has been demonstrated [10, 14] that the electromagnetic quantum vacuum, composed of *kenons* (7a) and (7b), complements naturally the normal ordering Hamiltonian in QED and describes a real physical vacuum state in both classical and quantum electromagnetic theories. In addition, it explains directly the vacuum effects such as the spontaneous emission and the Lamb shift [10, 11, 14] as well as the Fulling-Davies-Unruh temperature [17] (see Appendices 2 and 3).

We have seen that photons are local oscillations of the electromagnetic quantum vacuum field, produced by the action of the angular frequency operator upon *kenons*, and propagate at the speed imposed by its intrinsic properties, the vacuum electric permittivity ϵ_0 and magnetic permeability μ_0 . On the other hand, from Heisenberg's energy-time uncertainty relation we deduce that the vector potential amplitude is also subject to a fluctuation uncertainty [10, 16, 17]

$$\delta E_k \cdot \delta t \sim \hbar \rightarrow \delta \alpha_{0k} \cdot \delta t \sim \xi \rightarrow \delta \omega_k \cdot \delta t \sim 1 \quad (13)$$

Consequently, due to the electromagnetic vacuum fluctuations (Dark Light fluctuations), space is permanently full of transient photons at all frequencies underlying the cosmic radiation background. Obviously, according to the uncertainty relation (13), the lower the frequency the longer the transient photons lifetime, which could explain the $1/f^n$ noise origin observed in astrophysical measurements.

We may assume that the probability for a transient k -mode photon spontaneous creation is proportional to $e^{-|\vec{\mathcal{E}}_k/\epsilon_m|}$, where $|\vec{\mathcal{E}}_k|$ is the transient photon electric field amplitude generated in space and ϵ_m is a mean photon electric field amplitude over the electromagnetic spectrum. Using the result (5), that the photon electric field amplitude is proportional to the square of the angular frequency, we get the electromagnetic vacuum fluctuations energy density [19] weighing the integration by the transient photon spontaneous creation probability $e^{-|\vec{\mathcal{E}}_k/\epsilon_m|} = e^{-\omega^2/\omega_m^2}$,

$$\rho_{vacuum} = \frac{\hbar}{\pi^2 c^3} \int_0^\infty e^{-\omega^2/\omega_m^2} \omega^3 d\omega = \frac{\hbar \omega_m^4}{2 \pi^2 c^3} = \frac{2}{\pi} \epsilon_0 \mu_0 e \xi \omega_m^4 \quad (14)$$

Note that the above calculation cannot be applied in the case of the zero-point energy term because it's an eigenvalue of the harmonic oscillator Hamiltonian corresponding to a stable eigenstate composed of all k -mode photons and consequently the weighing factor is 1 for all frequencies.

Now, considering that ω_m is a logarithmic mean value of the angular frequency over the electromagnetic spectrum, that could be roughly in the THz region $\omega_m \sim 2\pi 10^{12} Hz$, we obtain $\rho_{vacuum} \sim 3 \cdot 10^{-10} J m^{-3}$ which is in good agreement with the astrophysical observations.

Consequently, the energy density of the electromagnetic quantum vacuum fluctuations (Dark Light fluctuations) is quite plausible to represent the Dark Energy considered responsible for the cosmic acceleration. On the other hand, residual photons of the electromagnetic vacuum fluctuations should emerge spontaneously in free space, which consequently should irradiate in the THz frequencies.

We expect the James Webb space telescope to provide an answer upon this.

2.2 Particles and antiparticles from the electromagnetic quantum vacuum. Mass-charge equivalence.

It has been established that the electron-positron elementary charge e , a fundamental physical constant, is obtained exactly from the electromagnetic vacuum quantized amplitude constant ξ [10, 17, 20]

$$e = (4\pi)^2 \alpha \frac{\xi}{\mu_0} \quad (15)$$

where, according to (2), $\xi < 0$ for the electron charge and $\xi > 0$ for the positron charge.

Note that the last relation, which expresses clearly the vacuum polarization, is neither a postulate nor a definition but derives naturally when considering the vector potential amplitude quantization at a single photon state (see Appendix 1).

It becomes evident that the photon vector potential amplitude $\alpha_{0k} = \xi\omega_k$ and the electron-positron elementary charge e are directly related to the electromagnetic quantum vacuum through the vacuum constant ξ demonstrating that photons and leptons-antileptons are physically strongly related entities and derive from the electromagnetic vacuum field, putting the basis for a physical comprehension of their mutual transformation mechanisms.

We recall that, from the historical experimental evidence, Planck's constant \hbar is intrinsically related to the energy quantization of the electromagnetic field at a single photon state. Despite of this characteristic physical origin Planck's constant is used in quantum physics for the description of all particles. Hence, we may guess that the electromagnetic nature should be an inherent property of particles.

In addition, it is important to mention that the notion of mass introduced in the expression of Bohr's magneton μ_B is a classical concept associated to a quantum process for the description of the magnetic dipole moment \vec{M} of a wave-particle with wave-vector \vec{k} in a circular standing state of radius r . In fact, in a pure quantum description Bohr's magneton is simply the proportionality constant of the magnetic dipole moment $\vec{M} = \mu_B(\vec{k} \times \vec{r})$.

Now, the mass m_{e^-,e^+} of the electron-positron is expressed exactly through the vacuum constant ξ , the elementary charge e and its magnetic moment

$$m_{e^-,e^+} = 2\pi c e^2 \frac{\xi}{\mu_B} \quad (16)$$

with $\mu_B = 9.274 \cdot 10^{-24} \text{ JT}^{-1}$ being the Bohr magneton.

Note that, according to (2), since $\xi < 0$ for the electron and $\xi > 0$ for the positron the masses m_{e^-} and m_{e^+} bear naturally opposite signs.

Also, the proton-antiproton mass writes

$$m_{p^+,p^-} = 2\pi c e^2 \frac{\xi}{\mu_p} \quad (17)$$

where $\mu_p = 5.0508 \cdot 10^{-27} \text{ JT}^{-1}$ is the proton magneton.

Similarly, the mass m_i of any elementary particle-antiparticle writes in a general way

$$m_i = 2\pi c e^2 \frac{\xi}{\mu_i} \quad (18)$$

where $\xi < 0$ for particles while $\xi > 0$ for antiparticles.

On the other hand, the magneton μ_i of any particle-antiparticle can be expressed approximately through Bohr's magneton μ_B and the fine structure constant α

$$\mu_i \approx \left(\frac{16\alpha}{n_i} \right) \mu_B \quad (19)$$

where n_i is simply a positive integer.

Thus, the mass of any particle i (other than the electron), that is lepton, meson or baryon, as well as of any antiparticle (other than the positron), is expressed uniquely with a precision better than 0.5% through the quantum vacuum constant ξ and by the same token through the electron-positron charge e [17]

$$m_i \approx n_i \sigma_\xi \xi = n_i \sigma_e e \quad (20)$$

with $\xi < 0$ for particles and $\xi > 0$ for antiparticles, while e is the electron or positron charge respectively.

The proportionality constants are:

$$\sigma_{\xi} = \pi c e^2 / 8\alpha\mu_B = 4.45110^{-5} \text{ kg} \cdot \text{kenon}^{-1} = \text{kg} \left(\text{V}^{-1} \text{m s}^{-2} \right)$$

$$\sigma_e = \hbar / 32\alpha\mu_B = 4.8696 \cdot 10^{-11} \text{ kg C}^{-1}$$

Equation (20) writes simply in MeV/c^2 units: $m_i \simeq 4.3767 n_i$.

It is worth noting that $4.3767 \text{ MeV}/c^2$ is roughly the mean mass of the down quark whose values lay in the interval $3\text{-}7 \text{ MeV}/c^2$.

In Table 1 are shown the masses obtained for different n_i values and the corresponding identified particles, considered conventionally positive.

Obviously, the rest masses of all particles-antiparticles emerge from the negative and positive components of the electromagnetic quantum vacuum field respectively and are purely of electromagnetic nature. The relations (18) and (20) express simply the mass-charge equivalence.

Although in table 1 we have considered the particles masses as positives according to the usual convention, it is important noting that the presence of either ξ or e in (20) confers an opposite sign between particles and antiparticles masses.

In fact, from equation (15) for the electron, ξ is negative and consequently the ordinary masses in equations (18) and (20) are negative and those of antimatter obtained from the positron charge are positive. This is because historically, a negative charge was conventionally attributed to the electron and a positive one to the positron.

According to the last equations, we draw that the electron-positron charge is directly related to photons and derive from the electromagnetic vacuum while the particles-antiparticles masses are quantum states of the vacuum field originating from charges and their magnetic moment.

In fact, the presence in equation (20) of an integer n_i characterizing the particles-antiparticles masses implies that the electromagnetic quantum vacuum must have a complex structure of quantum levels yet to discover, which might be related to string theory.

Quarks and antiquarks should be also states of the same vacuum field since they bear a fractional elementary charge ($e/3$ and $2e/3$) and consequently, strong and weak forces should be particular manifestations of the electromagnetic vacuum field. Through this lens, all neutral elementary particles-antiparticles must be composed of positive and negative charges and consequently, gravity should have electromagnetic nature.

n_i	m_i calculated (MeV c ⁻²)	m_i experimental (MeV c ⁻²)	$\delta(\%)$	particle
24	105.0	105.65	-0.57	Muon (lepton), μ^-
31	135.6	134.97	0.46	Pion (meson), π^0
32	140.0	139.57	0.30	Pion (meson), π^+, π^-
113	494.5	493.68	0.17	Kaon (meson), K^+, K^-
114	498.9	497.70	0.24	Kaon (meson), K_s^0, K_L^0
125	547.1	547.75	-0.11	Eta (meson), η^0
177	774.7	775.8	-0.14	Rho (meson), ρ^0, ρ^+, ρ^-
179	783.4	782.59	0.10	Omega (meson), ω
214	936.6	938.27	-0.17	Proton (baryon), p^+
215	940.9	939.56	0.15	Neutron (baryon), n^0
255	1116.0	1115.68	0.03	Lambda (baryon), Λ^0
271	1186.0	1189.37	-0.28	Sigma (baryon), Σ^+
272	1190.4	1192.6	-0.18	Sigma (baryon), Σ^0
273	1198.9	1197.45	0.12	Sigma (baryon), Σ^-
300	1313.0	1314.8	-0.13	Xi (baryon), Ξ^0
302	1321.7	1321.7	0.00	Xi (baryon), Ξ^-
350	1531.8	1531.8	0.00	Xi (baryon), Ξ^0 resonance
351	1536.2	1535.0	0.07	Xi (baryon), Ξ^- resonance
382	1671.9	1672.45	-0.03	Omega (baryon), Ω^-
406	1776.9	1777.0	-0.00	Tau (lepton), τ^-
426	1864.5	1864.8	-0.01	D Meson, D^0
450	1969.5	1968.4	0.05	Ds Meson, D_s^+
458	2004.5	2006.97	-0.12	D Meson, D^{*0}
459	2008.9	2010.27	-0.06	D Meson, D^{*+}
522	2284.6	2286.46	-0.08	Lambda c (baryon), Λ_c^+

n_i	m_i calculated (MeV c ⁻²)	m_i experimental (MeV c ⁻²)	$\delta(\%)$	particle
560	2451.0	2452.9 ; 2453.7	-0.08	Sigma c (baryon), Σ_c^+ , Σ_c^0
561	2455.3	2453.9	0.05	Sigma c (baryon), Σ_c^{++}
564	2468.4	2467.9	0.02	Xi c (baryon), Ξ_c^+ , Ξ_c^0
565	2472.8	2471.0	0.07	Xi c (baryon), Ξ_c^+ , Ξ_c^0
588	2573.5	2575.7	-0.08	Xi c (baryon), Ξ_c^+ resonance
589	2577.9	2578.0	-0.00	Xi c (baryon), Ξ_c^0 resonance
616	2696.0	2697.5	-0.06	Omega c (baryon), Ω_c^0
804	3518.9	3518.9	0.00	Xi cc (baryon), Ξ_{cc}^+
827	3619.5	3621.4	-0.05	Xi cc (baryon), Ξ_{cc}^{++}
1206	5278.3	5279.34 ; 5279.65	-0.02	B Meson, B^+ , B^0
1226	5365.8	5366.8	-0.02	Bs Meson, B_s^0
1284	5619.7	5620.2	-0.00	Lambda 0s (baryon), Λ_b^0
1327	5807.9	5810.5	-0.04	Sigma b (baryon), Σ_b^+
1329	5816.6	5815.2	0.02	Sigma b (baryon), Σ_b^-
1356	5934.8	5935.0	-0.00	Xi' b (baryon), Ξ_b'
1361	5956.6	5955.3	0.02	Xi* b (baryon), Ξ_b^*
1381	6044.2	6046.0	-0.02	Omega b (baryon), Ω_b^-
1423	6228.0	6226.9	0.01	Xi b (baryon), Ξ_b
1434	6276.1	6274.9	0.02	Bs Meson, B_c^+
18,367	80,386.8	80,385	+0.00	W ⁻ Boson
20,835	91,188.5	91,187.5	+0.00	Z Boson
28,581	125,090.4	125,090	-0.00	Higgs Boson

Table 1. Identification of particle masses obtained using equation (20) with different values of integers n_i and comparison to the experimental values. The discrepancy is lower than 0.2% for roughly 90% of the identified particles.

Finally, we may draw that fluctuations of the electromagnetic vacuum may also give birth to transient states in space of particles-antiparticles, corresponding to known and unknown particles. Halos of transient particles concentrations could be strongly favored near important real charges (mass) distributions and consequently might contribute to the Dark Matter.

2.3 Electromagnetic nature of the gravitational constant G .

Newton's and Coulomb's laws equivalence. Conditions for matter-antimatter antigravity.

Planck's length $l_p = 1.616 \cdot 10^{-35} m$, is a physical parameter corresponding to the shorter possible photon wavelength beyond which the electromagnetic energy density transforms to a black hole and consequently characterizes the granularity of the electromagnetic quantum vacuum.

Thus, considering Planck's length the gravitational constant G can be expressed exactly through the elementary charge e and the electromagnetic vacuum constants ξ , ε_0 and μ_0 [17]

$$G = \frac{l_p^2}{4\pi \varepsilon_0 \mu_0 e \xi} = \frac{l_p^2}{4\pi \varepsilon_0 \alpha (4\pi \xi)^2} \quad (21)$$

The masse-charge equivalence and the electromagnetic nature of the gravitation constant G imply the equivalence of Newton's gravitation law to Coulomb's electrostatic law. In fact, the well-known Newton's gravitational potential between two particles i and j with respective masses m_i and m_j separated by a distance r_{ij} writes [21]

$$U_{Newton} = G \frac{m_i m_j}{r_{ij}} = \frac{1}{4\pi \varepsilon_0} \frac{e_i e_j}{r_{ij}} \eta_{ij} = U_{Coulomb} \quad (22)$$

where we have used the relations (2), (18) and (21).

Note that e_i and e_j denote the electron charge for the particles or the positron charge for antiparticles while η_{ij} is a dimensionless parameter characterizing the nature of the interacting particles and depending on their magnetic moments.

$$\eta_{ij} = \frac{\pi \hbar c l_p^2}{\mu_0 \mu_i \mu_j} \quad (23)$$

Note also that, when considering the algebraic sign of charges, and not their absolute values as usually, a minus sign has to be considered in Coulomb's law in the electrostatic theory for the resulting positive potential to characterize attraction (as in gravitation) and the negative one repulsion (as in anti-gravitation).

According to equation (22) the gravitational potential writes now in pure electromagnetic terms

$$U = \frac{\hbar^2}{4} G \frac{e_i e_j}{r_{ij} \mu_i \mu_j} \quad (24)$$

and for a large number of particles

$$U = \frac{\hbar^2}{4} G \sum_{i,j(i<j)} \frac{e_i e_j}{r_{ij} \mu_i \mu_j} \quad (25)$$

We have used μ_B and l_p as intermediate constants in order to obtain physically meaningful relations expressing the mass-charge equivalence by equation (18) and the approximate expression (20), the electromagnetic nature of the gravitational constant G by equation (21) and the Newton-Coulomb potential equivalence by (22).

We recall here that Bohr's magneton μ_B is generally considered as a positive quantity so as the Larmor angular frequencies $\omega_L = \mu_B |\vec{B}| / \hbar$ for the elementary charge in a magnetic field \vec{B} to be also positive and the corresponding absorbed and emitted photons to have positive energies $\hbar \omega_L$. Under this condition, considering that the magnetons μ_i of the particles are positive quantities we can draw a quite interesting feature concerning matter, antimatter and gravity. In fact, for ε_0 and μ_0 to be positive in equations (10), e and ξ should have the same sign.

In this way, the gravitational constant expressed by (21) is positive for both matter and antimatter. Gravitation forces are attractive between bodies of ordinary matter, as well as between bodies of antimatter, but they should be repulsive between matter and antimatter according to Newton's gravitational potential (22) since they have "positive" and "negative" masses following the relation (20). However, this depends on the fundamental question on the sign of the particles-antiparticles magnetic moments and more precisely on the sign of the product $\mu_i\mu_j$ in equations (23) and (24).

In fact, previous studies that have shown that CPT symmetry (Charge conjugation, Parity and Time reversal) and General Relativity cannot be compatible unless matter and antimatter are mutually repelled [22]. We expect the ALPHA-g, AEGIS and GBAR experiments at CERN to give a definite answer to that issue.

Also, $\varepsilon_0, \mu_0, \mu_B, G$ as well as the photon frequencies and energies are positive and identical for matter and antimatter. However, due to ξ signs, the vector potential as well as the electric and magnetic fields of photons emitted by matter have opposite signs with respect to those emitted by antimatter, which might constitute an experimental criterion for exploring antimatter structures in the universe.

According to the established equations (2), (11), (15) and (21), the fundamental constants $c = (\varepsilon_0\mu_0)^{-1/2}$, $e = (4\pi)^2\alpha\xi / \mu_0$, $\hbar = \alpha\xi^2(4\pi)^3\varepsilon_0^{-1/2}\mu_0^{-3/2}$ and $G = l_p^2 / 4\pi\varepsilon_0\alpha(4\pi\xi)^2$ are expressed uniquely through the vacuum physical parameters $\varepsilon_0, \mu_0, \xi$ and l_p entailing that electromagnetism and gravitation are natural manifestations of the electromagnetic quantum vacuum field that may constitute the basic step towards a unified field theory.

Now, it is important remarking that equation (22) simply transposes the problem of gravitation without giving a clear idea about its real physical origin. In other words, we have switched from the unknown reason why masses attract (or repel) each other to the unknown reason why the ratios of charge to the magnetic moments should attract (or repel) each other.

In fact, using (20) the gravitational potential (25) writes

$$U \simeq \sigma_e^2 e^2 G \sum_{i,j(i<j)} \frac{s_{ij}n_i n_j}{r_{ij}} \quad (26)$$

where s_{ij} is the sign of the product $e_i e_j$ and n_i, n_j are the corresponding integers.

Obviously, unless pure integers attract or repel each other, Newton's and Coulomb's law are phenomenological mathematical expressions describing "how" gravitation and electrostatic forces act but without explaining physically "why".

In addition, it is worth to note that G in equation (21) is inversely proportional to $(4\pi\xi/l_p)^2$ which may be understood as the square of the linear density (in any direction) of the vacuum states. Generalizing the expression, we may write

$$G = \frac{1}{4\pi\varepsilon_0\alpha\rho(\xi)^2} \quad (27)$$

where $\rho(\xi)$ is the local *kenon* mean linear density.

Through this lens, G depends directly on the local density of the vacuum states and consequently may not be a universal constant. This could explain the gravitational anomalies observed on hundreds of galactic systems in contradiction with Newtonian dynamics and General Relativity. On the other hand, recent studies over 193 high-quality disk galaxies have finally ruled out with a high degree of statistical accuracy all modified Newtonian dynamics models [23].

Under these conditions, it is worth investigating whether gravitation might originate from the radiation pressure of the electromagnetic quantum vacuum field (*Electromagnetic Push Gravity*) felt by the bodies in their own frame and depending on the collective frequencies of their own charge densities [16].

In fact, a plasma is characterized by the plasma frequency ω_p corresponding to a collective oscillation frequency of the electron density n_e , whose well-known expression is

$$\omega_p = \left(n_e e^2 / \varepsilon_0 m_e \right)^{1/2} \quad (28)$$

Similarly, whatever the temperature, all the bodies are composed of charge densities whose collective oscillations yield characteristic global frequencies, analogue to the plasma frequency. For instance, the electron density in iron is roughly $2 \cdot 10^{29} m^{-3}$. Assuming that the plasma frequency expression (28) is valid, the angular frequency obtained for the iron is roughly $\omega_{iron} \approx 3 \cdot 10^{16} Hz rad$, which lays in the UV region.

Thus, every mass is characterized by one or more charge density collective frequencies and the *kenons* of the electromagnetic quantum vacuum field are “felt” in the mass frame as photons at the same collective frequencies inducing a radiation pressure.

Considering that a mass is characterized by a collective frequency ω_c , taking into account the two circular polarizations of kenons and the fact that the photon electric field experienced in the frame of the mass is proportional to $\xi \omega_c^2$, according to (5), the pressure dP exerted by the *kenons* upon the mass in a solid angle $d\Omega$ writes

$$dP_{vacuum} = \left(4\varepsilon_0 \xi^2 \omega_c^4 \right) d\Omega \quad (29)$$

The origin of gravitation appears to lay on the flow of *kenons* from the surrounding space towards the charge density (mass) which consequently experiences in its frame a radiation pressure at the characteristic frequency ω_c .

Variations to quantum vacuum field density may also be due to the presence of electromagnetic waves (photons) sources, which also reduce the local density of *kenons* since they transform *kenons* to photons enhancing by this way the gravitational effect at short distance. For instance, the photospheres of stars increase the gravitational effect felt by the bodies moving closely (perihelion). Similarly, light rays should follow the paths in the electromagnetic vacuum imposed by the charge densities in space modifying locally the vacuum density of states and the refractive index.

As an example, we may attempt to evaluate in a first approximation what could be the characteristic collective frequency of the Earth’s charge density by considering the system Sun-Earth.

The characteristic distances of the system are:

Radius of the Earth $R_E = 6.37 \cdot 10^6 m$, Radius of the Sun $R_S = 6.96 \cdot 10^8 m$ and the mean distance

Sun-Earth $R_{S-E} \approx 1.5 \cdot 10^{11} m$. Let us denote the collective frequency of the charge densities of the Earth by ω_E .

Consequently, the screening of the Sun, being considerably more important than that of the Earth, induce a force on the Earth towards the Sun due to the radiation pressure of the *kenons* flux coming from the opposite side of the Earth-Sun axe which writes in a first approximation

$$\delta F \approx 4\varepsilon_0 \xi^2 \omega_E^4 \left(\frac{\pi R_S^2}{R_{S-E}^2} \right) 2\pi R_E^2 = 8\pi^2 \varepsilon_0 \xi^2 \omega_E^4 \frac{R_S^2 R_E^2}{R_{S-E}^2} \quad (30)$$

Obviously, except the characteristic collective frequency, the geometry of the bodies plays also an important role.

We obtain a total attraction force exerted on the Earth due to the vacuum pressure induced by the presence of Sun equivalent to the Newtonian one $3.5 \cdot 10^{22} N$ for $\omega_E \sim 2\pi \cdot 10^{17} Hz rad$ which lays in the far UV region.

Using the same formalism a similar result is obtained for the system Earth-Moon considering the lunar characteristic frequency ω_L . The distances are: Radius of the Earth $R_E = 6.37 \cdot 10^6 m$, Radius of the Moon $R_M = 1.74 \cdot 10^6 m$ and the mean distance Earth-Moon $R_{E-M} = 3.8 \cdot 10^8 m$.

We get

$$\delta F \approx 8\pi^2 \varepsilon_0 \varepsilon^2 \omega_L^4 \frac{R_L^2 R_E^2}{R_{E-L}^2} \quad (31)$$

The attraction force is equivalent to the Newtonian one $2 \cdot 10^{20} N$ for $\omega_L \sim 2\pi \cdot 5 \cdot 10^{16} Hz$ rad which also lays in the UV region.

Despite the extreme simplicity of the above calculations, the obtained results seem to be rather physical since the plasma frequency corresponding to the electron density in metals is also in the UV region.

The precise knowledge of the characteristic frequencies and the geometry could yield results that are more accurate by considering the mutual screening effects of all the interacting bodies.

Thus, a well-elaborated model of *Electromagnetic Push Gravity*, analogue to that developed recently [24] for the Push Gravity, could be interesting to be developed and tested.

3. The electromagnetic quantum vacuum cosmic source of photons and particles-antiparticles.

Qualitative Principles of Quantum Vacuum Cosmology.

We have seen that transient states of the Dark Light fluctuations might be at the origin of Dark Energy and might contribute to Dark Matter.

Now, we may assume that a small part of the electromagnetic quantum vacuum fluctuations can indeed remain in space as residual real states. Certainly, this conflicts with the mass-energy and charge conservation laws but, as we will see later, these laws are satisfied between the initial and final states of the overall cosmic process. This statement constitutes the basis for a Quantum Vacuum Cosmological model whose main principles are described qualitatively below.

Real photons as well as particles and antiparticles, can be created continuously in space as residues of the electromagnetic quantum vacuum fluctuations. Thus, the vacuum turns out to be a cosmic source of photons (energy) as well as matter and antimatter.

As we have seen above, the photons generated by such a process should have a maximum energy density in the THz frequencies. The James Webb space telescope could provide useful measurements confirming or not this hypothesis.

On the other hand, the particles-antiparticles generated by the vacuum fluctuations residues might be in thermal equilibrium at $\sim 3 K^\circ$, which could explain the homogeneous and isotropic Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB).

Quantum vacuum fluctuations residues everywhere in an infinite and eternal space create photons and particles-antiparticles continuously, entailing that universe is homogeneous and flat. Obviously, the photon density is considerably more important than the particles-antiparticles ones. At the present state of investigations, the photos of the most distant galaxies taken by the James Webb space telescope do not show any hints of the Big Bang process entailing that the universe components are the same everywhere.

Some particle-antiparticles pairs annihilate producing photons, others combine progressively to electrons-protons and positrons-antiprotons forming respectively hydrogen and antihydrogen atoms, then molecules and gas which are progressively separated by gravitational repulsion to form distant accumulations, the first with ordinary matter and the second with antimatter. Under the effect of gravity, following the *kenon* push gravity, the increasing concentrations of hydrogen (antihydrogen) give birth to stars (antimatter stars, 'anti-stars'). Next, heavier elements (anti-elements) are produced in stars (anti-stars) by the also well-known baryon (anti-baryon) genesis process. Galaxies (antimatter galaxies, 'anti-galaxies') and clusters of galaxies (anti-galaxies) are formed progressively. Universe is thus composed of systems of matter and antimatter. We may reasonably assume that antimatter stars and galaxies should have the same birth, life and death as the ordinary matter ones, as well as similar radiation properties

yielding a particular difficulty for their detection. In fact, various studies have shown that antihydrogen atoms have the same properties with those of ordinary hydrogen atoms and particularly the same energy levels [25, 26]. At the present state of observational techniques, it is impossible to distinguish the photons emitted by matter or antimatter. As mentioned above, new methods based on the positive or negative photons vector potentials could probably support the observational investigation for exploring the antimatter distributions in the universe.

The quantum vacuum pressure, yields a cosmic expansion and acceleration. Recent works [27] have shown that Hubble law and acceleration curve emerge in a repulsive matter-anti matter galaxies simulations. Thus, if matter-antimatter gravitational repelling is confirmed experimentally then it certainly contributes to the cosmic expansion enhancing the quantum vacuum effect.

Finally, the surprising homothetic structural similarities between Deoxyribonucleic Acid (DNA) and photons and the continuous coupling to *kenons* raises the question whether the triggering of life, at least in the form met in our planet, is also related to the electromagnetic quantum vacuum [28].

Energy-mass annihilation mechanisms, like black holes (antimatter black holes, ‘anti black holes’) and probably other yet unknown cosmic structures, appear in the universe following the death of massive stars (anti-stars), mostly in the center of galaxies (anti-galaxies). Obviously, such annihilation mechanisms appear to older galaxies, which could explain why quasars are found in big distances. The cosmic energy-mass annihilation mechanisms transform the initially spontaneously generated energy-mass back to the quantum vacuum state, which also explains simply what the huge amounts of energy and mass absorbed by black holes become in the singularity.

In an infinite and eternal universe it is not evident to ascertain if there was a starting time to this process consisting of energy-matter-antimatter spontaneous creation from the quantum vacuum and annihilation towards the same quantum vacuum field.

Epilogue

We have visited the basic physical features that derive naturally from the electromagnetic quantum vacuum, the cosmic Dark Light, composed of real states called *kenons*. Local oscillations of *kenons* over a wavelength at an angular frequency ω_k give birth to a real vector potential, thus to real photons (electromagnetic waves) guided by the non-local vector potential wave function with the quantized amplitude $\alpha_{0k} = \xi\omega_k$. The vacuum electric permittivity and magnetic permeability, ϵ_0 and μ_0 respectively, are intrinsic properties of the electromagnetic quantum vacuum and fix the speed of photons in vacuum c .

The electromagnetic quantum vacuum is a cosmic field, with positive and negative components, permeating everything in the universe and whose fluctuations last longer the lower the frequency. This could also explain the origin of the $1/f^n$ noise observed not only in astrophysics but also in many other technological fields.

Positive and negative elementary charges are states of the positive and negative components respectively of the electromagnetic quantum vacuum field and are strongly related to photons vector potential through the vacuum constant ξ .

The masses of all particles and antiparticles originate also from the negative and positive vacuum field respectively. The mass-charge equivalence relation results directly expressing that the masses of all particles-antiparticles derive from charges and their magnetic moments. Hence, the electromagnetic vacuum should have a complex structure with quantum levels that may be related to the string theory.

The gravitational constant G is also related to the vacuum electromagnetic properties implying that Newton's gravitational potential is equivalent to Coulomb's electrostatic potential. We deduce that gravitation has electromagnetic nature and the gravitational constant G is the same for matter and antimatter. However, the masses of particles and antiparticles bear naturally opposite signs entailing that if their magnetic moment product is positive then it yields a mutual gravitational repulsion. Finally, the generalization of the gravitational constant formula indicates that G is inversely proportional to the square of the vacuum density of states (*kenons* density) and consequently may not be a universal constant.

It is of high importance to mention that we have made no hypothesis and advanced no axioms or postulates in order to obtain the above results. Everything derives naturally from Maxwell's theory once the vector potential amplitude is normalized at a single photon level. The established formalism links the electromagnetic vacuum to electromagnetism, particle physics and gravitation. Consequently, the electromagnetic quantum vacuum field may constitute the physical basis for the development of a coherent unified field theory.

Dark Energy and Dark Matter might both originate from transient states of Dark Light fluctuations. The first due to transient photons and the second to transient pairs of known and unknown particles. Weighing the electromagnetic vacuum fluctuations energy density, we deduced that the electromagnetic energy density of the quantum vacuum fluctuations should have a maximum in the THz region. Under these conditions, free space is not Lorentz invariant and an observer with uniform velocity, in absence of any other reference frame, would be able to detect his motion from the Doppler shift of the electromagnetic vacuum fluctuations spectrum.

We have drawn that transient photons due to vacuum fluctuations, that we identified to Dark Energy, and the eventual matter-antimatter repelling represent the physical mechanisms that might be at the origin of the observed cosmic acceleration.

Next, we advanced two hypothesis:

- a. *Gravitation is due to the electromagnetic quantum vacuum (kenons) radiation pressure (Electromagnetic Push Gravity) experienced by the charge densities (mass) in their frame at their own collective oscillation frequencies.*

Using a simple screening model, we have analyzed in a first approximation the possibility of the "Electromagnetic Push Gravity" due to the electromagnetic quantum vacuum (*kenons*). The flux of *kenons* towards a localized charge density (mass), induces in its frame a radiation pressure at the characteristic charge density collective frequency.

An intense source of photons, depleting continuously the vacuum states, exhibits also a direct gravitational effect, such as photospheres in stars corona. Light rays follow the paths in the electromagnetic vacuum imposed by the charge densities in space modifying locally the vacuum states (*kenons*) and consequently the vacuum fluctuations and the refractive index.

The approximated characteristic collective frequencies calculated for Earth and Moon lay in the UV spectrum and are slightly higher than the plasma frequencies attributed to metals.

- b. *Photons as well as matter and antimatter emerge spontaneously in universe from the electromagnetic quantum vacuum as residues of its associated fluctuations.*

Everything in universe derives from the electromagnetic quantum vacuum, the Dark Light composed of *kenons*.

The spectral density of free space should have a maximum in the THz frequency region.

The spontaneously generated particles-antiparticles are at thermal equilibrium at $\sim 3 \text{ K}^\circ$.

Energy-mass annihilation mechanisms, such as black holes, appear naturally during the evolution of stars (anti-stars) and galaxies (anti-galaxies) transforming the initially spontaneously generated energy-

mass back to the vacuum state. This also provides a satisfactory explanation to what the tremendous quantities of energy-mass swallowed by black holes become in the singularity. Energy-mass and charges are conserved between the initial and final states of the overall cosmic creation-annihilation processes.

A quantum vacuum cosmological model could be developed on this basis overcoming the well-known Big Bang inconveniences such as, initial state, faster than the speed of light inflation, as well as the horizon, flatness and antimatter issues.

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The **appendices** that follow are joint with the aim to help the reader understanding better the theoretical background used in this paper.

More extensive developments can be found in:

- *Light and Vacuum*, Constantin Meis, 2nd Edition, World Scientific, Singapore (2017).
- *Quantized field of single photons*, Constantin Meis, in Single Photon Manipulation, IntechOpen, London (2019), Ed. Prof. Keyu Xia, Nanjing University, China. DOI: 10.5772/intechopen.88378, ISBN: 978-1-83880-353-7. Open Access. <https://www.intechopen.com/online-first/quantized-field-of-single-photons>
- *Primary role of the quantum electromagnetic vacuum in Gravitation and Cosmology*, Constantin Meis, in Cosmology 2020 – The Current State, IntechOpen, London (2020), Ed. Michael L. Smith, USA. DOI: 10.5772/intechopen.87805. ISBN: 978-1-83968-267-4. Open Access <https://www.intechopen.com/online-first/cosmology-2020-the-current-state>

APPENDIX 1

- *Vector potential quantization, photon wave-particle equation and wave function*

A general solution of the vector potential $\vec{A}(\vec{r}, t)$ is obtained from Maxwell's equations and writes

$$\vec{A}(\vec{r}, t) = \frac{\mu}{4\pi} \int \frac{\vec{J}(\vec{r}', t - \frac{|\vec{r} - \vec{r}'|}{c})}{|\vec{r} - \vec{r}'|} d^3r' \quad (1.1)$$

A simple dimension analysis of the last expression shows that the vector potential is proportional to a frequency. Hence, we may write for the vector potential amplitude $\alpha_{0k}(\omega_k)$ of a single k -mode photon with angular frequency ω_k

$$\alpha_{0k}(\omega_k) = \xi \omega_k \quad (1.2)$$

where ξ is a constant to be determined.

Thus, the equation with the fundamental physical quantities characterizing both the particle (energy and momentum) as well as the wave (vector potential, wave vector and dispersion relation) nature of a single k -mode photon is now completed by introducing the missing electromagnetic nature of a single photon through the vector potential amplitude

$$\frac{E_k}{\hbar} = \frac{|\vec{p}_k|}{\hbar/c} = \frac{\alpha_{0k}}{\xi} = \frac{|\vec{k}|}{\sqrt{\epsilon_0 \mu_0}} = |\vec{k}|c = \omega_k \quad (1.3)$$

An interesting feature results by considering that the photon momentum $|\vec{P}_k|$ has the units of a mass m_k times the velocity c in vacuum so we may write $|\vec{P}_k| = \hbar k = m_k c$. Of course, m_k is simply a dimensional parameter here since the photon is generally considered to be a massless particle. Using $E_k = \hbar \omega_k = \hbar k c$ one gets directly $E_k = m_k c^2$ showing that the energy-mass equivalence is a direct result of the wave-particle double nature of light since we have used the wave dispersion relation $\omega_k = |\vec{k}|c$ and the momentum $|\vec{P}_k| = \hbar |\vec{k}|$ which is a particle property.

Now, the photon vector potential may be written in a general plane wave expression with the quantized amplitude

$$\vec{\alpha}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t) = \omega_k \left(\xi \hat{\epsilon}_\lambda e^{i(\vec{k} \cdot \vec{r} - \omega_k t + \phi)} + cc \right) = \omega_k \vec{\Xi}_{k\lambda}(\omega_k, \vec{r}, t) \quad (1.4)$$

with λ the polarization (circular left or right), $\hat{\epsilon}_\lambda$ the polarization complex unit vector, ϕ a phase parameter and cc the complex conjugate.

It is physical for the photon vector potential function $\alpha_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t)$ to satisfy the wave propagation equation in vacuum

$$\vec{\nabla}^2 \vec{\alpha}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t) - \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} \vec{\alpha}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t) = 0 \quad (1.5)$$

The second derivative with respect to time is proportional to the square of the amplitude and we get

$$\frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} \vec{\alpha}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t) = -\omega_k^2 \vec{\alpha}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t) = -\left(\frac{\alpha_{0k}}{\xi} \right)^2 \vec{\alpha}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t) \quad (1.6)$$

The propagation equation now writes

$$\left[\alpha_{0k}^2 + \xi^2 c^2 \vec{\nabla}_k^2 \right] \vec{\alpha}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t) = 0 \quad (1.7)$$

entailing that the photon vector potential amplitude can be expressed as an operator $\tilde{\alpha}_{0k}$ proportional to the constant ξ

$$\tilde{\alpha}_{0k} = -i\xi c \vec{\nabla}_k \quad (1.8)$$

which is valid for any mode k . Obviously, the established vector potential amplitude operator is quite symmetrical with the relativistic Hamiltonian for a massless particle

$$\tilde{H}_k = -i\hbar c \vec{\nabla}_k \quad (1.9)$$

Application of $\tilde{\alpha}_{0k}$ upon $\vec{\alpha}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t)$ along the propagation axis induce a phase variation getting

$$\tilde{\alpha}_{0k} \vec{\alpha}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t, \varphi) = i\xi c k \vec{\alpha}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t, \varphi + \frac{\pi}{2}) \quad (1.10)$$

However, for the time variation we also get

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \vec{\alpha}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t, \varphi) = \omega_k \vec{\alpha}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t, \varphi + \frac{\pi}{2}) \quad (1.11)$$

Combination of the last two equations gives a linear time differential equation for the photon vector potential

$$i\xi \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \vec{\alpha}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t) = \tilde{\alpha}_{0k} \vec{\alpha}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t) \quad (1.12)$$

Consequently, the *vector potential – energy* (wave – particle) equation for the photon is obtained straight forward by associating Schrödinger's equation and writes

$$i \left(\frac{\xi}{\hbar} \right) \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \vec{\alpha}_{k,\lambda}(\vec{r}, t) = \left(\begin{array}{c} \tilde{\alpha}_{0k} \\ \tilde{H}_k \end{array} \right) \vec{\alpha}_{k,\lambda}(\vec{r}, t) \quad (1.13)$$

where

$$\left(\begin{array}{c} \tilde{\alpha}_{0k} \\ \tilde{H}_k \end{array} \right) = -i \left(\frac{\xi}{\hbar} \right) c \vec{\nabla}_k \quad (1.14)$$

are the k -mode photon vector potential amplitude and the Hamiltonian operators.

- **Definition of the vector potential amplitude quantization constant ξ**
- **Electron-positron charge from the electromagnetic quantum vacuum**

Considering the photon as an integral particle, the integration of the energy density should give the single photon energy $E_k = \hbar\omega_k$, so we have

$$\int \varepsilon_0 \omega_k^2 \alpha_{0k}^2(\omega_k) \left[\hat{\varepsilon}_\lambda e^{i(\omega_k t - \vec{k} \cdot \vec{r} + \varphi)} + c.c \right]^2 d^3 r = \hbar\omega_k \quad (1.15)$$

For the last relation to hold at any instant t the photon polarization unit vector $\hat{\varepsilon}_\lambda$ should have at least two orthogonal components, \hat{e}_1 and \hat{e}_2 , such as $\hat{\varepsilon}_\lambda = \sigma_1 \hat{e}_1 + \sigma_2 \hat{e}_2$ with $|\sigma_1|^2 + |\sigma_2|^2 = 1$ and $\hat{e}_1 \cdot \hat{e}_2 = 0$

. Accordingly, right (R) and left (L) hand circular polarization unit vectors, $\hat{\varepsilon}_{L,R} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (\hat{e}_1 \pm i\hat{e}_2)$ are

naturally appropriate to satisfy this condition and equation (1.15) becomes

$$\int 2\varepsilon_0 \omega_k^2 \alpha_{0k}^2(\omega_k) d^3 r = \hbar\omega_k \quad (1.16)$$

It has been demonstrated that a k -mode photon cannot be considered as an integral entity within a length smaller than its wavelength λ_k [1.1]. Furthermore, Compton has demonstrated the directional character

of photons experimentally. Thus, the integration of the left hand side of equation (1.16) may be carried out in cylindrical coordinates (ρ, θ, z) , where z is the propagation axis along which the vector potential rotates perpendicularly. In a full period interval, $0 \leq z \leq \lambda_k$, the angular coordinate θ is related to z by $\theta = 2\pi z / \lambda_k$ and the integration may be reduced to the variables, z and ρ in the limits $0 \leq z \leq \lambda_k$ and $0 \leq \rho \leq \eta \lambda_k$, with η a positive dimensionless constant characterizing the radial spatial extension of the photon.

Using (1.2) we get

$$2\varepsilon_0 \omega_k^2 \alpha_{0k}^2(\omega_k) \left(\frac{\eta^2}{2} \lambda_k^3 \right) = (2\pi c)^3 \varepsilon_0 \xi^2 \eta^2 \omega_k = \hbar \omega_k \quad (1.17)$$

Hence, the product of the two constants η and ξ has the value

$$\eta \xi = \pm \frac{1}{(2\pi)^{3/2}} \sqrt{\frac{\hbar}{\varepsilon_0 c^3}} \quad (1.18)$$

Now, equation (1.17) can be written with a slight rearrangement as follows

$$4\pi c \left(\frac{1}{4\pi c} 2\varepsilon_0 \omega_k^2 \alpha_{0k}(\omega_k) \left(\frac{\eta^2}{2} \lambda_k^3 \right) \right) \alpha_{0k}(\omega_k) = 4\pi c Q \alpha_{0k}(\omega_k) = \hbar \omega_k \quad (1.19)$$

making to appear a parameter Q which has charge units.

Considering the square of Q and using (1.2) and (1.18) we get

$$Q^2 = \left(\frac{1}{4\pi c} 2\varepsilon_0 \omega_k^2 \alpha_{0k}(\omega_k) \left(\frac{\eta^2}{2} \lambda_k^3 \right) \right)^2 = \frac{\eta^2}{4} (\varepsilon_0 h c) \quad (1.20)$$

where h is Planck's constant.

Using for η the experimental approximate value of $\sim 1/4$ [1.2-1.4] we obtain directly the numerical value

$$Q \simeq \pm 1.6 \cdot 10^{-19} C \quad (1.21)$$

which is the electron-positron charge, a physical constant, appearing naturally here when considering the quantization of the vector potential amplitude at a single photon level.

This signifies that the physical origin of the elementary charge is strongly related to the photon vector potential and to the electromagnetic quantum vacuum.

Based on this result we can go further in the definitions of both η and ξ constants by the intermediate of the electron charge expressed through the fine structure constant $\alpha = e^2 / 4\pi\varepsilon_0 \hbar c$

$$\frac{\eta^2}{4} (\varepsilon_0 h c) = 2\alpha (\varepsilon_0 h c) \quad (1.22)$$

getting

$$\eta = \sqrt{8\alpha} \quad (1.23)$$

Consequently, from (1.18) we get the value of ξ

$$\xi = \pm \frac{1}{(2\pi)^{3/2}} \sqrt{\frac{\hbar}{8\alpha \varepsilon_0 c^3}} = \frac{\hbar}{4\pi e c} = 1.747 \cdot 10^{-25} \text{ Volt } m^{-1} s^2 \quad (1.24)$$

The single k -mode photon quantization volume writes

$$V_k = \left(\frac{\eta^2}{2} \lambda_k^3 \right) = 4\alpha \lambda_k^3 \quad (1.25)$$

A similar result for the single photon quantization volume can be obtained from the density of states theory. In fact, the number of photons $dn(\omega)$ in the quantization volume V in the frequency interval between ω and $\omega + d\omega$ is

$$dn(\omega) = V \frac{\omega^2}{\pi^2 c^3} d\omega \quad (1.26)$$

Thus,

$$n(\omega) = 4V \frac{\omega^3}{3\pi^2 c^3} \quad (1.27)$$

where the factor 4 takes into account the two possible values of spin ($\pm\hbar$) and the propagation directions ($\pm z$). For $n(\omega) = 1$ the corresponding quantization volume for a k -mode photon writes

$$V_k = \left(\frac{3}{4} \pi^2 c^3 \right) \omega_k^{-3} \quad (1.28)$$

With $\lambda_k^3 = (2\pi c)^3 \omega_k^{-3}$ we get

$$V_k = \frac{3}{32\pi} \lambda_k^3 \simeq 4\alpha \lambda_k^3 \quad (1.29)$$

Finally, from (1.20), (1.23) and (1.24) it is straightforward to obtain the electron-positron charge depending uniquely on the electromagnetic quantum vacuum constants

$$e = \pm (4\pi)^2 \alpha \frac{\xi}{\mu_0} \quad (1.30)$$

The last relation demonstrates that the elementary charge is a state of the electromagnetic quantum vacuum strongly related to the single photon vector potential amplitude.

- **Photon wave-particle properties and Heisenberg's uncertainty**

The particle properties, energy, momentum and spin of a k -mode photon are not carried by a point particle but by a wave-corpuscle and can be expressed in terms of the quantisation volume.

As we have seen above, the energy of a single photon can be obtained as follows

$$E_k = \int_{V_k} 2\varepsilon_0 \alpha_{0k}^2 \omega_k^2 d^3r = \int_{V_k} 2\varepsilon_0 \xi^2 \omega_k^4 d^3r = 2\varepsilon_0 \xi^2 \omega_k^4 V_k = \hbar \omega_k \quad (1.31)$$

With the same token considering a circular polarization the momentum writes

$$\vec{P}_k = \int_{V_k} \varepsilon_0 \vec{\varepsilon}_{k\lambda} \times \vec{\beta}_{k\lambda} d^3r = \varepsilon_0 \left(\sqrt{2} \omega_k \alpha_{0k} \right) \left(\frac{1}{c} \sqrt{2} \omega_k \alpha_{0k} \right) V_k \frac{\vec{k}}{|\vec{k}|} = \hbar \vec{k} \quad (1.32)$$

where $\vec{\varepsilon}_{k\lambda}$ and $\vec{\beta}_{k\lambda}$ denote the electric and magnetic fields of a single mode k .

According to the classical electromagnetic theory the spin can be written through the electric and magnetic fields components

$$\vec{S} = \int_{V_k} \varepsilon_0 \vec{r} \times \left(\vec{\varepsilon}_{k\lambda} \times \vec{\beta}_{k\lambda} \right) d^3r = \pm \varepsilon_0 \left(\frac{c}{\omega_k} \right) \left(\sqrt{2} \omega_k \alpha_{0k} \right) \left(\frac{1}{c} \sqrt{2} \omega_k \alpha_{0k} \right) V_k = \pm \hbar \quad (1.33)$$

where we have considered the property [1.6] that the mean value of the length in a k -mode photon state is c/ω_k .

The quantization volume V_k appears to be an intrinsic property for a single photon and defines the minimum space in which the quantized electric and magnetic fields oscillate at the frequency ω_k over a wavelength λ_k along the propagation axis. It may also ensure the link with the particle representation. In fact, when introducing the particle operators single photon vector potential amplitude operators expressed through the creation and annihilation non-Hermitian operators

$$\tilde{\alpha}_{0k} = \xi \omega_k a_{k\lambda} \quad ; \quad \tilde{\alpha}_{0k}^* = \xi \omega_k a_{k\lambda}^+ \quad (1.34)$$

into the quantum electrodynamics position and momentum operators, one directly gets the corresponding position $\hat{Q}_{k\lambda}$ and momentum $\hat{P}_{k\lambda}$ operators,

$$\hat{Q}_{k\lambda} = \sqrt{\varepsilon_0 V_k} (\tilde{\alpha}_{0k} + \tilde{\alpha}_{0k}^*) \quad \hat{P}_{k\lambda} = -i\omega_k \sqrt{\varepsilon_0 V_k} (\tilde{\alpha}_{0k} - \tilde{\alpha}_{0k}^*) \quad (1.35)$$

The demonstration of Heisenberg's commutation relation, a fundamental concept in quantum theory, is straightforward

$$[\hat{Q}_{k\lambda}, \hat{P}_{k'\lambda'}] = -i\varepsilon_0 \omega_k^2 \omega_{k'} \sqrt{V_k V_{k'}} \left[(\xi a_{k\lambda} + \xi^* a_{k\lambda}^+), (\xi a_{k'\lambda'} - \xi^* a_{k'\lambda'}^+) \right] = i\hbar \delta_{kk'} \delta_{\lambda\lambda'} \quad (1.36)$$

showing the consistency of the above formalism.

- **Photon wave function**

- a. *Previously suggested photon wave functions from the electric and magnetic fields*

In quantum theory, all particles with non-zero mass in a quantum state are characterized by a wave function $\Psi(\vec{r}, t)$, depending on space and time, which satisfies Schrödinger's equation with eigenvalues the energy corresponding to a given quantum state. The photon, as a relativistic massless particle, constitutes a particular case and the proposed wave functions published in the literature until now are not in general satisfactory. An important theoretical difficulty, among others, lays in the fact that the photon is not a "localizable particle" and consequently a position operator cannot be defined. Nevertheless, some fruitful attempts have already been done for establishing a photon wave function and are given in the bibliography [1.7-1.12]. The most pertinent theoretical developments are based on the complex vector function $\vec{F}(\vec{r}, t)$ initially introduced by Riemann

$$\vec{F}(\vec{r}, t) = \frac{1}{2\sqrt{\varepsilon_0}} \vec{D}(\vec{r}, t) + i \frac{1}{2\sqrt{\mu_0}} \vec{B}(\vec{r}, t) \quad (1.37)$$

where the electric displacement flux density $\vec{D}(\vec{r}, t)$ and the magnetic field flux density $\vec{B}(\vec{r}, t)$ are defined respectively through the electric and magnetic fields intensities $\vec{E}(\vec{r}, t)$ and $\vec{H}(\vec{r}, t)$ following the expressions

$$\vec{D}_{\alpha\beta}(t) = \hat{\varepsilon}_{\alpha\beta} \cdot \vec{E}_{\alpha\beta}(t) \quad ; \quad \vec{B}_{\alpha\beta}(t) = \hat{\mu}_{\alpha\beta} \cdot \vec{H}_{\alpha\beta}(t) \quad (1.38)$$

with the electric permittivity $\hat{\varepsilon}_{\alpha\beta}$ and magnetic permeability $\hat{\mu}_{\alpha\beta}$ being tensors ($\alpha = x, y, z$ and $\beta = x, y, z$) characterizing the intrinsic electric and magnetic nature of the medium in which the electric and magnetic field intensities subsist.

At that point it is important to mention that the electric field $\vec{E}(\vec{r}, t)$ and the magnetic induction $\vec{B}(\vec{r}, t)$ are fundamental fields while $\vec{D}(\vec{r}, t)$ and $\vec{H}(\vec{r}, t)$ are fields that include the response of the medium at macroscopic level. In isotropic media, that is in media in which the electric and magnetic properties are identical in all spatial directions, the electric field is parallel to the electric displacement and the magnetic field flux intensity parallel to the magnetic field

$$\vec{D}(\vec{r}, t) = \varepsilon \vec{E}(\vec{r}, t) \quad \vec{H}(\vec{r}, t) = \frac{1}{\mu} \vec{B}(\vec{r}, t) \quad (1.39)$$

Using the complex function $\vec{F}(\vec{r}, t)$ Maxwell's equations in an homogeneous medium become

$$i \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \vec{F}(\vec{r}, t) = c \vec{\nabla} \times \vec{F}(\vec{r}, t) \quad (1.40)$$

$$\vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{F}(\vec{r}, t) = 0 \quad (1.41)$$

In this way, a suggested photon wave function was defined as

$$\Psi(\vec{r}, t) = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{2\sqrt{\epsilon_0}} \vec{D}(\vec{r}, t) + i \frac{1}{2\sqrt{\mu_0}} \vec{B}(\vec{r}, t) \\ \frac{1}{2\sqrt{\epsilon_0}} \vec{D}(\vec{r}, t) - i \frac{1}{2\sqrt{\mu_0}} \vec{B}(\vec{r}, t) \end{pmatrix} \quad (1.42)$$

which is a six component vector satisfying Schrödinger's equation in the form

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \Psi(\vec{r}, t) = c \begin{pmatrix} -i\hbar \vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{S} & 0 \\ 0 & i\hbar \vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{S} \end{pmatrix} \Psi(\vec{r}, t) \quad (1.43)$$

where \vec{S} is the spin matrix for a spin 1 particle with the Cartesian components

$$S_x = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -i \\ 0 & i & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad S_y = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & i \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -i & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad S_z = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -i & 0 \\ i & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (1.44)$$

The square modulus of the above defined photon wave function $\Psi(\vec{r}, t)$ provides the classical electromagnetic field energy density $W(\vec{r}, t)$ at an instant t and at a given coordinate \vec{r} on the propagation axis

$$|\Psi(\vec{r}, t)|^2 = W(\vec{r}, t) = \frac{1}{2} \left(\epsilon_0 |\vec{E}(\vec{r}, t)|^2 + \frac{1}{\mu_0} |\vec{B}(\vec{r}, t)|^2 \right) \quad (1.45)$$

Obviously, the energy can be expressed directly by integrating in space the bilinear form of the complex vector function $\vec{F}(\vec{r}, t)$ getting

$$E = \int \vec{F}^*(\vec{r}, t) \cdot \vec{F}(\vec{r}, t) d^3r \quad (1.46)$$

However, the relations (1.45) and (1.46) give respectively the energy density and the energy of the electromagnetic field but not precisely those of a single photon state.

Furthermore, in quantum mechanics, the integration in space of the square modulus of the normalized photon wave function, given by (1.42), should correspond to the probability of localizing a photon and not to the energy of the classical electromagnetic field representation. In a characteristic single photon quantization volume on the propagation axis this quantity should be equal to unity and this is not really the case here for $\Psi(\vec{r}, t)$.

Finally, some different versions from the one described above have been advanced for the photon wave function but without introducing a real progress in the whole problematics.

b. Photon wave function from the vector potential quantization

The vector potential function $\vec{\alpha}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t)$ with the quantized amplitude $\xi \omega_k$ can be considered as a real wave function for the photon and can be suitably normalized [1.13]. In fact, when a k -mode photon is emitted at a coordinate \vec{r} at an instant t and propagates in vacuum the probability to be localized at time t' at the coordinate $\vec{r}' = \vec{r} + c(t'-t)\hat{r}$ corresponds to the square of the modulus of the vector potential and it is consequently proportional to the square of the angular frequency

$$|\vec{\alpha}_{k\lambda}(z, t)|^2 = \xi^2 \omega_k^2 \propto \lambda_k^{-2} \quad (1.47)$$

It is evident that the higher the frequency, the shorter the wavelength of the photon and the higher the localization probability in agreement with Heisenberg's uncertainty and the experimental evidence.

The photon momentum is $\vec{p}_k = \hbar \vec{k} = (\hbar / \lambda_k) \hat{k}$ and Heisenberg's uncertainty for the position and momentum for a photon writes simply

$$\delta z \delta p_{k_z} \geq h \rightarrow \delta z \delta (1 / \lambda_k) \geq 1 \quad (1.48)$$

where we have considered the propagation along the z -axis.

Hence, the physical meaning of Heisenberg's relation is that the photon cannot be localized precisely on the propagation axis except with a significant uncertainty which is of the order of the wavelength λ_k . This physical situation has been confirmed experimentally and is a natural consequence laying in the intrinsic wave-particle nature of the photon. As frequently quoted, despite the fact that the *point-particle* model used in the QED formalism is a practical mathematical tool, in reality the photon cannot be defined within a length shorter than its wavelength and is localized only within a volume proportional to λ_k^3 .

Now, taking into account the above facts and weighting the vector potential function by the factor $(\varepsilon_0 \omega_k / \hbar)^{1/2}$ we may define a general wave function for the photon [1.14]

$$\Phi_{k,(L,R)}(\vec{r}, t) = \left(\frac{\varepsilon_0 \omega_k}{\hbar} \right)^{1/2} \left[\alpha_{0k}(\omega_k) \left(\hat{\varepsilon}_{k,(L,R)} e^{i(\vec{k} \cdot \vec{r} - \omega_k t)} + \hat{\varepsilon}_{k,(L,R)}^* e^{-i(\vec{k} \cdot \vec{r} - \omega_k t)} \right) \right] \quad (1.49)$$

where the circular polarization can be either left (L) or right (R).

Obviously, $\Phi_{k,(L,R)}(\vec{r}, t)$ satisfies also the wave propagation equation (1.5) and the *vector potential – energy* equation (1.13). Whatever the circular polarization, the square of the modulus of the normalized general wave function (1.49) gives the inverse of the single photon quantization volume

$$\left| \Phi_{k,(L,R)}(\vec{r}, t) \right|^2 = \frac{\varepsilon_0 \omega_k}{\hbar} \left[\xi^2 \omega_k^2 \left(\left| \hat{\varepsilon}_{k,(L,R)} \right|^2 + \left| \hat{\varepsilon}_{k,(L,R)}^* \right|^2 \right) \right] = \frac{2 \varepsilon_0 \xi^2 \omega_k^3}{\hbar} = \frac{1}{V_k} \quad (1.50)$$

so that

$$\int_{V_k} \left| \Phi_{k,(L,R)}(\vec{r}, t) \right|^2 d^3 r = 1 \quad (1.51)$$

The probability to find the photon in the volume V_k around the coordinate \vec{r} on the propagation axis equals one.

Note that $\Phi_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t)$ is defined at an instant t at the coordinate r . However, the photon may only be defined in V_k around r and its physical properties are obtained by integration of the wave properties over V_k as we have seen above. Consequently, a position operator cannot be defined due to the photon intrinsic volume V_k . By this way, the mean values of the quantum mechanics operators can be applied with a particular manner in the case of the photon by considering the quantization volume V_k .

The mean value of the relativistic massless particle Hamiltonian writes

$$\begin{aligned} \left| \langle \Phi_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t) | \tilde{H}_k | \Phi_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t) \rangle_{V_k} \right| &= \left| \langle \Phi_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t) | -i \hbar c \vec{\nabla}_k | \Phi_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t) \rangle_{V_k} \right| \\ &= \varepsilon_0 \xi^2 \omega_k^4 V_k \left| \left(e^{i(\vec{k} \cdot \vec{r} - \omega_k t)} \hat{\varepsilon}_{k\lambda} + e^{-i(\vec{k} \cdot \vec{r} - \omega_k t)} \hat{\varepsilon}_{k\lambda}^* \right) \left(e^{i(\vec{k} \cdot \vec{r} - \omega_k t)} \hat{\varepsilon}_{k\lambda} - e^{-i(\vec{k} \cdot \vec{r} - \omega_k t)} \hat{\varepsilon}_{k\lambda}^* \right) \right| \\ &= \varepsilon_0 \xi^2 \omega_k^4 V_k \left| \left(e^{2i(\vec{k} \cdot \vec{r} - \omega_k t)} - e^{-2i(\vec{k} \cdot \vec{r} - \omega_k t)} \right) \right| = 2 \varepsilon_0 \xi^2 \omega_k^4 V_k \left| \sin 2(\vec{k} \cdot \vec{r} - \omega_k t) \right| \\ &= \hbar \omega_k \left| \sin 2(\vec{k} \cdot \vec{r} - \omega_k t) \right| \end{aligned} \quad (1.52)$$

The function $\left| \sin 2(\vec{k} \cdot \vec{r} - \omega_k t) \right|$ is a phase function (varying from 0 to 1) which means that when

$\left| \sin 2(\vec{k} \cdot \vec{r} - \omega_k t) \right| = 1$ corresponds to the “phase-matching” with the quantization volume V_k around r .

In this case, the mean value of the Hamiltonian is the single photon energy $\hbar \omega_k$ and the momentum operator is

$$\left| \langle \Phi_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t) | \vec{p}_k | \Phi_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t) \rangle_{V_k} \right| = \left| \langle \Phi_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t) | -i\hbar \vec{\nabla}_k | \Phi_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t) \rangle_{V_k} \right| = \frac{\hbar \omega_k}{c} \quad (1.53)$$

and the energy density for a single photon is

$$W_k = |\Phi_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t)|^2 \left| \langle \Phi_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t) | \tilde{H}_k | \Phi_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t) \rangle_{V_k} \right| = \frac{\hbar \omega_k}{V_k} = 2\varepsilon_0 \xi^2 \omega_k^4 \quad (1.54)$$

which is proportional to ω^4 as in the case of a classical radiating dipole.

Consequently, the photon wave function defined in (1.49) obtained from the vector potential quantization at a single photon level, satisfies the propagation equation, the vector potential – energy equation, the normalized probability condition and represents a real eigenstate of the relativistic massless particle Hamiltonian and the corresponding momentum operator with eigenvalues $\hbar \omega_k$ and $\hbar |\vec{k}|$ respectively.

Appendix 1 - Bibliography

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APPENDIX 2

- *Fulling-Davies-Unruh temperature in the electromagnetic quantum vacuum*

Any particle moving in the electromagnetic field ground state with an acceleration $\vec{\gamma}$ experiences an electric potential

$$U = |\xi \vec{\gamma}| \quad (2.1)$$

Notice that even for high relativistic values, of the order of $|\vec{\gamma}| \propto 10^7 m s^{-2}$, the electric potential felt by the accelerated particle is very low $U \propto 10^{-18} V$.

For a charge e the corresponding energy along a given degree of freedom is equivalent to a thermal energy according to the equipartition theorem

$$E = |e \xi \vec{\gamma}| = \frac{1}{2} k_B T \quad (2.2)$$

where k_B is Boltzmann's constant.

Replacing ξ in the last equation by the expression, $\xi = \hbar / 4\pi |e| c$ we get directly the Fulling-Davies-Unruh temperature

$$T = \frac{\hbar}{2\pi c k_B} |\vec{\gamma}| \quad (2.3)$$

This extremely simple calculation shows that an accelerated charge in the electromagnetic field ground state will “feel” the Fulling-Davies-Unruh temperature.

APPENDIX 3

In the following, we calculate the vacuum effects, spontaneous emission and Lamb shift, due to the electromagnetic quantum vacuum $\Xi_{0,\lambda}$. We do not deal with the Casimir effect since it has been clearly demonstrated [3.1 – 3.4] that its physical origin lays on the source fields and Lorentz's forces. However, the Casimir effect may also be interpreted as the radiation pressure difference between the inner and outer space of the conducting plates due to photons “seen” in the electromagnetic quantum vacuum field by the electrons having a periodic motion on the inner and outer surfaces of the plates.

- *The electromagnetic quantum vacuum and the spontaneous emission*

We recall the total Hamiltonian of an atom in the presence of an electromagnetic field in the dipole approximation writes:

$$H_{tot} = H_{Electromagnetic_Field} + H_{interaction} + H_{atom} = \sum_{k,\lambda} \hbar \omega_k \left(\tilde{n}_{k\lambda} + \frac{1}{2} \right) - \vec{D} \cdot \vec{E}(\vec{r}, t) + \sum_i \hbar \omega_i |\Psi_i\rangle \langle \Psi_i| \quad (3.1)$$

Where we have used the harmonic Hamiltonian representation for the electromagnetic field including the zero-point energy, $\vec{D} = e\vec{r}$ is the dipole moment of an atomic electron of charge e and $|\Psi_i\rangle$ the atomic levels with the corresponding energies $\hbar \omega_i$.

The spontaneous emission rate is always calculated in QED *neglecting* $\sum_{k,\lambda} \frac{1}{2} \hbar \omega_k$ in $H_{Electromagnetic_Field}$

(since it is an infinite quantity) and using the following expression for the electric field $\vec{E}(\vec{r}, t)$ resulting from Heisenberg's equation of motion.

$$\vec{E}(\vec{r}, t) = -\frac{\partial \vec{A}(\vec{r}, t)}{\partial t} = \frac{i}{\hbar} \left[\vec{A}(\vec{r}, t), \sum_{k,\lambda} \hbar \omega_k \left(\tilde{n}_{k\lambda} + \frac{1}{2} \right) \right] \quad (3.2)$$

Consequently, for the calculation of the electric field attributed to the vacuum state the term $\sum_{k,\lambda} \frac{1}{2} \hbar \omega_k$ should be the principal contribution to the interaction Hamiltonian. However, the commutation operator of the vector potential and the vacuum zero-point Hamiltonian cancels

$$\left[\vec{A}(\vec{r}, t), \sum_{k,\lambda} \frac{1}{2} \hbar \omega_k \right] = 0 \quad (3.3)$$

because the zero-point energy $\sum_{k,\lambda} \frac{1}{2} \hbar \omega_k$ is a constant and consequently this term has absolutely no contribution in the general expression of the quantized electric field used to calculate the spontaneous emission in QED.

Indeed, in a rigorous calculation the interaction Hamiltonian between an atomic electron and the vacuum writes

$$H_{\text{interaction}} = -\vec{d} \cdot \frac{i}{\hbar} \left[\vec{A}(\vec{r}, t), \sum_{k,\lambda} \frac{1}{2} \hbar \omega_k \right] = 0 \quad (3.4)$$

which also vanishes in QED as in the semi-classical description and this fact is scarcely quoted in the literature.

The physical reason is that in QED the vacuum state Hamiltonian is not described by a function of $a_{k\lambda}$ and $a_{k\lambda}^+$ operators and consequently it is impossible to define an interaction Hamiltonian for the description of the electron-vacuum interaction processes. Conversely, the electromagnetic field ground state (described by equation 7b in this paper) does indeed depend on the photon creation and annihilation operators permitting to define a "vacuum action" operator [3.5-3.6] corresponding to an interaction Hamiltonian per angular frequency between the vacuum field $\tilde{\Xi}_{0\lambda}$ and an atomic electron of mass m_e and charge e

$$H_{\omega_k} = \frac{\hbar e}{m_e c} \tilde{\Xi}_{0\lambda} \tilde{\Omega}_k = -i\hbar \frac{e}{m_e} \tilde{\Xi}_{0\lambda} \cdot \vec{\nabla} \quad (3.5)$$

Thus, the amplitude of the transition probability per angular frequency between an initial state $|\Psi_i, 0\rangle$ with total energy $E_i = \hbar \omega_i$, corresponding to an atom in the state $|\Psi_i\rangle$ with energy E_i in vacuum $|\dots, 0_{k\lambda}, \dots, 0_{k'\lambda'}, \dots\rangle$, and a final state $|\Psi_f, n_{k\lambda}\rangle$ with total energy $E_{f, n_{k\lambda}} = \hbar \omega_f + n_{k\lambda} \hbar \omega_k$ representing the atom in the state $|\Psi_f\rangle$ with energy $E_f = \hbar \omega_f$ in the presence of $n_{k\lambda}$ photons, can be expressed in first order time dependent perturbation theory

$$c_{\omega_k}^{(1)}(t) = -\frac{e}{m_e} \int_0^t \left[\langle \Psi_f, n_{k\lambda} | \xi \vec{\mathcal{E}}_{k\lambda} \cdot \vec{\nabla} a_{k\lambda} | \Psi_i, 0 \rangle e^{i(\omega_i - \omega_f - n_{k\lambda} \omega_k)t'} + \langle \Psi_f, n_{k\lambda} | \xi^* \vec{\mathcal{E}}_{k\lambda}^* \cdot \vec{\nabla} a_{k\lambda}^+ | \Psi_i, 0 \rangle e^{-i(\omega_i - \omega_f - n_{k\lambda} \omega_k)t'} \right] dt' \quad (3.6)$$

Since $a_{k\lambda}|\Psi_i,0\rangle = 0$, using the fundamental definition of the momentum operator $\vec{P} = -i\hbar\vec{\nabla}$ as well as Heisenberg's equation of motion $\vec{p} = m\frac{d}{dt}\vec{r} = -m\frac{i}{\hbar}[\vec{r}, H_0]$ the scalar product of the equation (1.6) corresponding to the creation operator $a_{k\lambda}^+$ writes

$$\langle \Psi_f, n_{k\lambda} | \xi^* \vec{\epsilon}_{k\lambda} \cdot \vec{\nabla} a_{k\lambda}^+ | \Psi_i, 0 \rangle = -\xi^* \delta_{1,n_{k\lambda}} m_e \omega_{if} \vec{\epsilon}_{k\lambda} \cdot \vec{r}_{if} / \hbar \quad (3.7)$$

with $\vec{r}_{if} = \langle \Psi_f | \vec{r} | \Psi_i \rangle$, $\omega_{if} = \omega_i - \omega_f$ and considering the expression of $\xi = \hbar / 4\pi e c$ we obtain the spontaneous emission rate in the elementary solid angle $d\Omega$

$$T_{emission}^{spontaneous} = \frac{e^2}{8\pi^2 \hbar \epsilon_0 c^3} \omega_{mi}^3 \int d\Omega \sum_{\lambda} |\vec{r}_{mi}|_{\lambda}^2 \cos^2 \theta = \frac{e^2}{3\pi \epsilon_0 \hbar c^3} \omega_{mi}^3 |\vec{r}_{mi}|^2 \quad (3.8)$$

where $\cos^2 \theta$ has been replaced by the mean value

$$\langle \cos^2 \theta \rangle = \frac{1}{4\pi} \int \cos^2 \theta d\Omega = \frac{1}{4\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} d\phi \int_{-1}^{+1} \cos^2 \theta d(\cos \theta) = \frac{1}{3} \quad (3.9)$$

Getting finally the well-known expression of the spontaneous emission rate within a solid angle $d\Omega$

$$W_{if} = \frac{1}{3\hbar c^3} \frac{e^2}{4\pi \epsilon_0} \omega_{if}^3 |\vec{r}_{if}|^2 d\Omega \quad (3.10)$$

- ***The electromagnetic quantum vacuum and the Lamb shift.***

W.E. Lamb and R.C. Rutherford measured precisely the energy difference between the levels 2S_{1/2} and 2P_{3/2} of the atomic hydrogen in 1947 using microwave technics. They obtained a value of $4.5 \cdot 10^{-5}$ eV, which was not explained by Dirac's theory which predict these two levels to have the same energy. From a theoretical point of view, although by introducing the kenon function in Bethe's calculations instead of the vector potential we get identical results we will not reproduce those calculations here. The reason is that Bethe's non-relativistic calculations for the Lamb shift, which many authors have discussed and commented, are based on a quite original method consisting of obtaining finite quantities by subtracting and neglecting infinite quantities. Therein, Dirac was the first to argue that *intelligent mathematics consists of neglecting negligible quantities and not infinite quantities because, simply, you do not want them*. Indeed, many authors remarked that in Bethe's method what is quite puzzling is that after manipulating and ignoring infinite quantities, after imposing arbitrary integration limits, after considering mean logarithmic values over an infinity of atomic energy levels near the continuum, ... "the final result compares "remarkably" well to the experiment".

Henceforth, we can now have a different look to the Lamb shift by applying a physically comprehensive method (without infinities and singularities) for the description of the interaction of the electromagnetic quantum vacuum state with the atomic energy levels [3.5, 3.6].

The energy shifts of the electron-bounded states can be seen as a topological effect of the vacuum radiation pressure upon the electronic orbitals. In fact, the vacuum is not composed of photons but of kenons. Thus, the motion of a bounded state electron with charge e , whose energy is E_{nlj} , in the vacuum field $\Xi_{0\lambda}$ is characterised by Bohr's angular frequency

$$\omega_{nlj} = \frac{E_{nlj}}{\hbar} = \frac{R_\infty}{n^2 \hbar} \quad (3.11)$$

where n, l, j are the quantum numbers of the corresponding orbital, R_∞ is Rydberg's constant and n an integer, the principal quantum number. This periodic motion of the electron in the field $\vec{E}_{0\lambda}$ yields the rise in its frame of a vector potential amplitude

$$\alpha_{0(nlj)} = \xi \omega_{(nlj)} \quad (3.12)$$

corresponding to "vacuum photons" with energy

$$4\pi e c \xi \omega_{nlj} = \hbar \omega_{nlj} \quad (3.13)$$

Hence, despite the fact that the vacuum state has no photons in the normal ordering Hamiltonian representation, an electron experiences in its frame vacuum photons due to its periodic motion whose radiation pressure per unit surface writes

$$dP_{vacuum} = \sum_{\lambda} \epsilon_0 \left| \vec{\mathcal{E}}_0^{(R,L)} \right|^2 d\Omega \quad (3.14)$$

where $\left| \vec{\mathcal{E}}_0^{(R,L)} \right|^2$ is the electric field amplitude of the left and right hand polarized vacuum photons seen by the electron in its frame.

Using the circular polarization components, we obtain for the square amplitude of the electric field

$$\left| \vec{\mathcal{E}}_0^{(R)} \right|^2 = \omega_{nlj}^2 \left(\left| \alpha_{x_0}^{(R)} \right|^2 + \left| \alpha_{y_0}^{(R)} \right|^2 \right) = \omega_{nlj}^2 \left(\left| \alpha_{x_0}^{(L)} \right|^2 + \left| \alpha_{y_0}^{(L)} \right|^2 \right) = \omega_{nlj}^2 \left(2\xi^2 \omega_{nlj}^2 \right) \quad (3.15)$$

Consequently, from (3.14) the summation over the two circular polarizations λ , R and L, and the summation over the whole solid angle gives the total vacuum radiation pressure

$$P_{vacuum} = 4\pi \epsilon_0 \left(4\xi^2 \omega_{nlj}^4 \right) = \frac{\hbar \omega_{nlj}^4}{4\alpha \pi^2 c^3} \quad (3.16)$$

Where α is the fine structure constant. Hence, if the electron moves in the effective volume $V_{nlj}(eff)$ of the nlj orbital the corresponding energy shift due to vacuum radiation pressure writes

$$\delta E = P_{vacuum} V_{nlj}(eff) \approx \frac{\hbar \omega_{nlj}^4}{4\alpha_{FS} \pi^2 c^3} V_{nlj}(eff) \quad (3.17)$$

A delicate operation consists of defining $V_{(nlj)}(eff)$. The nS electronic orbitals for example are characterised by a density probability distribution decreasing smoothly with an exponential expression. Furthermore, for the excited electronic nS states the radial wave functions contain negative values and the electron probability density distribution involves a significant space area with zero values. Hence, in the case of atomic hydrogen for the spherically symmetrical electronic orbitals nS , in order not to take into account the space regions where the probability density is zero, the effective volume may be written in a first approximation

$$V_{(nS)}(eff) \approx \frac{1}{n} \frac{4}{3} \pi \left| \langle \psi_{nS} | r | \psi_{nS} \rangle \right|^3 \quad (3.18)$$

and following the last two equations the corresponding frequency of the energy shift

$$\nu_{nS} = \frac{\delta E_{(nS)}}{h} \approx \frac{\omega_{nS}^4}{6\alpha \pi^2 c^3} \frac{1}{n} \left| \langle \psi_{nS} | r | \psi_{nS} \rangle \right|^3 \quad (3.19)$$

Putting $\omega_{nS} = \frac{R_\infty}{n^2 \hbar}$ with $R_\infty = 13.606 \text{ eV}$, and considering the cube of the mean value of the distance in the hydrogen electronic orbitals nS

$$\left| \langle r \rangle_{n,l=0}^3 \right| = \left| \int \Psi_{(n,l=0)} r \Psi_{(n,l=0)}^* d^3 r \right|^3 = a_0^3 \left(\frac{3n^2}{2} \right)^3 \quad (3.20)$$

with $a_0 = 0.53 \cdot 10^{-10} m$ being the first Bohr radius, the frequency of the energy shift writes

$$V_{nS} \simeq \frac{1}{n^3} \frac{9 R_\infty^4 a_0^3}{16 \alpha \pi^2 c^3 \hbar^4} \quad (3.21)$$

Significant Lamb shifts have been observed for the nS orbitals (n being the principal quantum number) having a spherical density probability distribution and zero orbital momentum $l = 0$.

We obtain the Lamb shifts frequencies for the hydrogen nS levels:

1S: ~ 7.96 GHz (8.2 GHz), 2S: ~ 1000 MHz (1040 GHz), 3S: ~ 296 MHz (303 MHz), 4S: ~ 124 MHz

where the experimental values are given in parenthesis.

Consequently, the energy shifts of the nS levels of the hydrogen atom interacting with vacuum can be estimated with a rather good approximation for such a simple calculation by considering the radiation pressure of the vacuum “seen” in the frame of the electrons due to their periodic motion in the vacuum field $\vec{E}_{0\lambda}$.

The above demonstrate that the electromagnetic quantum vacuum, the Dark Light composed of kenons, complements remarkably well the normal ordering Hamiltonian of the electromagnetic field and lifts the corresponding ambiguities in QED.

Appendix 3 - Bibliography

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